

DEVELOPMENT OF YOUNG LEARNERS’ SPEECH THROUGH TEACHING SPEAKING

Sulaymanova Barno Rakhmatillaevna

PhD student of Tashkent State Pedagogical University, sulaymanovabarno@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10818683>

***Annotatsiya.** Nutq mahorati 21-asr davrida har bir bola egallashi kerak bo'lgan to'rtta qobiliyatdan biriga aylanadi. Muloqot, hamkorlik, til chegaralari turli va ko'p millatli xalqlarda zaruratga aylanadi. Ushbu tadqiqot o'qituvchining yosh o'quvchilarga so'zlashish ko'nikmasini o'rgatish strategiyalari, muammolari va echimlarini o'rganishga qaratilgan. Ushbu tadqiqot ishi yosh o'quvchilarga nutqni o'rgatishda o'qituvchi sinfdagi mashg'ulotlarda rolli o'yin, video tomosha qilish, raqamli hikoyalar, o'yinlar va takrorlash kabi bir nechta strategiyalardan foydalangan. O'qituvchilar sinfda nafaol, talaffuzida ko'p hatolari mavjud va so'z boyligi kam bo'lgan o'quvchilar ishlenganda bir qator to'siqlarga duch kelishlari mumkin. Ammo u bu to'siqlarni yosh o'quvchilarga nutqini rivojlantirib, so'zlashga o'rgatishning turli usullaridan, masalan, ommaviy axborot vositalaridan foydalanish va mavzuga asoslangan o'quv materiallaridan foydalangan holda darsni loyihalash orqali engib o'tishi mumkin.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** so'zlashish ko'nikmasi, boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari, kommunikativ kompetentsiya*

***Abstract.** The proficiency of speaking becomes one of the five skills that should be acquired by every child in this 21 century era. Communicating and collaborating and language boundaries become a necessity in diverse and multinational communities. This research is aimed to investigate the teacher's strategies, problems and solutions for teaching speaking to young learners. A case study design was used in this study, and the data were collected through observation. This research has showed when teaching speaking to young learners. In the classroom activities, the teacher used several strategies such as, role play, watching videos, digital storytelling, games, and repetition. The teachers might face several barriers in the classroom such as reluctant students, missing pronunciation and lack of vocabularies. But she can overcome those barriers by using various techniques of teaching speaking to young learners, such as implementing media and designing the lesson using topical-based syllabus.*

***Key words:** speech, speaking, young learners, communicative competence*

***Аннотация.** Умение говорить становится одним из четырех навыков, которые должны быть приобретены каждым ребенком в эту эпоху 21 века. Коммуникация, сотрудничество и языковые границы становятся необходимостью в различных и многонациональных сообществах. Цель этого исследования заключается в изучении стратегий, проблем и решений преподавателя в отношении обучения молодых учащихся. В рамках этого исследования использовался план тематического исследования, а сбор данных осуществлялся с помощью наблюдений. Это исследование было продемонстрировано при обучении молодых учащихся. В учебных занятиях учитель использовал несколько стратегий, таких как ролевые игры, просмотр видео, цифровое повествование, игры и повторение. Преподаватели могут сталкиваться в классе с рядом препятствий, таких как нежелание учащихся, отсутствие произношения и нехватка словарей. Но она может преодолеть эти барьеры, используя различные методы обучения, говорящие с молодыми учениками, такие как использование СМИ и разработка урока с использованием тематической программы.*

Ключевые слова: речь, молодые ученики, коммуникативная компетентность

Introduction

English is becoming the primary language used for communication in both local and international contexts in the modern day of globalization. Therefore, it is essential that English be used effectively everywhere. With a lack of native tongue, teaching and studying English is therefore essential for communication in order to meet the rising local, national, and worldwide demand for English proficiency. The process of learning English is slow and progressive and it could be interpreted as a series of challenges to face. This process consists of the development of certain skills. According to the common framework, these are divided into productive and receptive. Receptive skills comprise reading and listening. They are important because they allow learners to understand contents, textbooks, works or documents. Productive skills are consist of speaking and writing and they are significant because they permit learners to perform in communicative aspects such as oral presentations, written studies and reports among others. Therefore, these skills need to be developed and learnt properly.

Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) is a method which is based on the target of language teaching and learning for effective and real life communication. According to Diane (2004: in Seraj and Mamun, 2011: p.8) the aim of CLT is to facilitate to communicate in target language. Communicative Competence is measured on the four basic skills of languagereading, writing, speaking and listening. As developing the ability of the learners to really communicate in English is the main goal of SSC syllabus, it is essential to integrate all four skills ensuring equal amount of concentration in each of them. Thus, the learners will have the level of linguistic competence in English that will enable them to communicate effectively in “real English” (Davis & Pearse, 2000; p.4). Here the expression “real English” is used to refer to English which can be used both inside and outside the classroom.

Teachers tend to talk about the way we use language in terms of four skillsreading, writing, speaking and listening. They are often divided into two types. Receptive skills is a term used for reading and listening, skills where meaning is extracted from the discourse. Productive skills is the term for speaking and writing, skills where students actually have to produce language themselves (Harmer, 2007, p.244). In preparing every child to have a good communication skill, teaching speaking is a primary requirement to be taught not only for adult learners but also for young learners. As stated by Slattery and Willis (2001), cited in Hakim (2011), English is being provided into initial classroom, such as Kindergarten and Elementary school, so that the teachers are needed to teach it into young learners. Further, to make the children to be able to speak English in communication, teachers need to guide the students to acquire the vocabulary and structures (Richard, 2008). Meanwhile, teaching speaking to young learners may give some difficulties to the teacher especially in Indonesia, since the young learners also consider speaking as a great challenge since it requires them to speak and think at the same time (Pinter, 2000). Besides, young learners are not necessarily competent communicators even in their mother tongue, and it reveals an idea that teaching speaking in Indonesia must be developed in EFL context.

Methods and Results

Speaking Skill

Speaking is the productive skill in the oral mode. It, like the other skills, is more complicated than it seems at first and involves more than just pronouncing words. According to

Chastain (1998), speaking is a productive skill that involves many components, such as grammar, strategy, sociolinguistics and discourse; for him speaking is more than simply making the right sounds, choosing the right words or getting the constructions correct (pp. 330-358). Speaking skill is required everywhere, from simple conversation to formal public speaking. As Wilson (1997: p.9) argues, talking can be used to connect with others, explore and understand the world and reveal oneself. In EFL context, the language users are also urged to speak in different genres and situation, and they will have to be able to use a range of conversational and conversational repair strategies (Harmer, 2007a).

Teacher Roles in Teaching Speaking to young learners

Paul (2003, p. 77) lists several principles that teachers need to consider in preparing students to communicate in English:

1. Introducing and practicing patterns in ways that feel meaningful to the children, such as in games, in situation where the children genuinely want to express themselves, and through personalization.

2. Practicing new patterns in combination with the other patterns the children have learned, so the children can internalize them more easily.

3. Giving the children many opportunities to guess how to use the patterns flexibly in novel situation.

4. Giving the children confidence to speak out in front of others by talking independently with other children and the whole class.

5. Building the children’s inner strength to deal with confusing and novel situations, by presenting them with puzzles to overcome and solve, and making sure they are finally successful.

Young learner is categorized as students from ages three to eight years old (Wilson, 2003; Alianello, 2004). Pinter (2006) limits the age groups of young learners from five to fourteen years old. However, she offers an idea that age of categorization is not a big deal in teaching language to young learners. The main issue in teaching language to young learners should begin with the consideration that every child is unique and they have substantial differences within, such as the culture differences (Pinter, 2006). Moreover, Paul (2000) adds that all children deserve the chance to achieve their potential both as learners and as whole people, and become broad-minded members of a truly international society.

Strategies in Teaching Speaking to Young Learners Teaching

Young learner is categorized as students from ages three to eight years old (Wilson, 2003; Alianello, 2004). Pinter (2006) limits the age groups of young learners from five to fourteen years old. However, she offers an idea that age of categorization is not a big deal in teaching language to young learners. The main issue in teaching language to young learners should begin with the consideration that every child is unique and they have substantial differences within, such as the culture differences (Pinter, 2006). Moreover, Paul (2000) adds that all children deserve the chance to achieve their potential both as learners and as whole people, and become broad-minded members of a truly international society.

Brain Storming On a given topic, students can produce ideas in a limited time. Depending on the context, either individual or group brainstorming is effective and learners generate ideas quickly and freely. The good characteristic of brainstorming is that the students are not criticized for their ideas so students will be open to sharing new ideas.

Simulations Simulations are very similar to role-plays but what makes simulations different than role plays is that they are more elaborate. In simulations, students can bring items to the class to create a realistic environment. For instance, if a student is acting as a singer, she brings a microphone to sing and so on.

Role Play Students pretend they are in various social contexts and have a variety of social roles. In role-play activities, the teacher gives information to the learners such as who they are and what they think or feel. Thus, the teacher can tell the student that "You are David, you go to the doctor and tell him what happened last night, and." (Harmer, 2007b)

Picture Describing For this activity students can form groups and each group is given a different picture. Students discuss the picture with their groups, and then a spokesperson for each group describes the picture to the whole class. This activity fosters the creativity and imagination of the learners as well as their public speaking skills.

Find the Differences For this activity students can work in pairs and each couple is given two different pictures, for example, picture of boys playing football and another picture of girls playing tennis. Students in pairs discuss the similarities and/or differences in the pictures.

Picture Narrating This activity is based on several sequential pictures. Students are asked to tell the story taking place in the sequential pictures by paying attention to the criteria provided by the teacher as a rubric. Rubrics can include the vocabulary or structures they need to use while narrating.

Assessing Young Learners' Speaking Proficiency

Assessment is an integral part of teaching and learning process. It can be described as the process of data analysis that teacher use to get evidence about their learners' performance and progress in English. Assessment has several roles, such as: to change people's lives, to examine, monitor and aid children's progress, to build an accurate and effective communication between teacher and parents ,to provide feedback on pupils' learning, and to monitor teacher's performance and plan future work (Ioannou-Georgiou & Pavlou, 2003).

Overall, the aim is to achieve oral communication, and the teacher should assess their communicative proficiency in basic functions, such as asking questions or introducing themselves.

CONCLUSION

These conclusions are directly appointed to research problems formulated earlier in the previous section, i.e. 1. What are the teacher's strategies in enhancing young learners' speaking proficiency? 2). What are the barriers faced by the teacher in teaching speaking? 3).How does the teacher overcome the barriers? This research has found several strategies promoted by the lecturer when teaching speaking to young learners. In the classroom activities, the teacher used several strategies such as, role play, watching videos, digital storytelling, games, and repetition. The teachers might face several barriers in the classroom such as reluctant students, missing pronunciation and lack of vocabularies. But he can overcome those barriers by using various techniques of teaching speaking to young learners, such as implementing media and designing the lesson using topical-based syllabus.Teaching speaking sounds easier since there are plenty of interesting techniques that can be employed in the classroom. However, there are still other considerations about teaching it to young learners. The teachers still need to take multiple-intelligence into account, because the teacher should meet each student's need in the classroom. There were several numbers of problems when this research was conducted such as the limited time for conducting the research and the lack of resources.

REFERENCES

1. Brown, Nation. “Teaching Speaking: Suggestion for the Classroom.” 4 January 2008 <http://jaltpublications.org/tlt/files/97/jan/speaking.html>>
2. Chastain, K. (1998). *Developing second language skills* (2nd Ed.). Chicago: Harcourt Brace Publishers.
3. Cohen & Manion. (1994). *Research methods in education* fourth edition. United States and Canada, Reprinted.
4. Creswell, J. W. (2002). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Person.
5. Chen, I.J. (2005). Using games to promote communicative skills in language learning. *The Internet TESL Journal*, 11 (2), Retrieved on November 10, 2014, from: <http://iteslj.org/Techniques/ChenGames.html>
6. Harmer, J. (2007a). *How to teach English*. Essex: Pearson Education Limited.
7. Paul, D. (2003). *Teaching English to young learners in Asia*. Hongkong: Longman Asia ELT.
8. Richards, J.C. (2006). *Developing classroom speaking activities: From theory to practice*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
9. Storyart.org. (2000). Why storytelling? Retrieved on November 10, 2011, from: <http://www.storyarts.org/classroom/>
10. Tompkins, P.K. (1998). Role-playing/ simulation. *The Internet TESL Journal*, 4 (8), Retrieved on November 10, 2011